

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Microporous Microgel Assemblies Facilitating the Recruitment and Osteogenic Differentiation of Progenitor Cells for Bone Regeneration

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Received: 22 May 2025 | **Revised:** 5 December 2025 | **Accepted:** 9 December 2025

Keywords: bone regeneration | microgels | micropores | mesenchymal stromal cells | recruitment | stiffness

ABSTRACT

Biomaterials for bone regeneration, additionally to providing structural support and delivering of key biological signals, must promote the recruitment and growth of local progenitor cells. While synthetic biomaterials are tailorable regarding stability and bioactivity, their mesh size often requires proteolytic remodeling for cells to infiltrate and thereby can significantly restrict the progress of regeneration. Here, to improve the recruitment of osteogenic cells, microporous biomaterials with various degrees of stiffness are formed by the confinement of transglutaminase crosslinked polyethylene glycol (TG-PEG) microgels. Confined microgels are found to be suitable substrates for human bone marrow stromal cells (hBM-MSCs), that with increasing stiffness reveal improved spreading, Yes-associated protein (YAP) activation, and heightened recruitment of cells mediated by platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF)-BB. Furthermore, upon stimulation with bone morphogenetic protein (BMP)-2, osteogenic differentiation of hBM-MSCs is found to be superior when cultured on stiff microgels as compared to encapsulation in bulk hydrogels. Even more compelling, TG-PEG microgels enable a stiffness-dependent recruitment of cells from bone defects *in vitro*. The combination of tunable stiffness and microscale pore structures in microgels provides new perspectives on the design of advanced scaffolds for bone healing, with the potential to improve clinical outcomes in regenerative medicine.

1 | Introduction

Bone healing involves a series of events, including provisional matrix formation, recruitment of progenitor cells, and their differentiation into functional tissue [1]. Biomaterials, used to fabricate scaffolds and hydrogels, were shown to play a crucial role in promoting bone healing by bridging the defect and mimicking the extracellular matrix (ECM) [2–4]. Various biomaterials properties, including the stiffness, *in vivo* stability, porosity, and cell adhesion sites were shown to influence the recruitment, infiltration, proliferation, differentiation, and

viability of healing-associated cells, including bone progenitor cells [5–7].

Granules and scaffolds made of tricalciumphosphate and hydroxyapatite with defined architectures and porosities have been successfully used for the closure and stabilization of bone defects [8]. Indeed, when designed with appropriate porosity, such biomaterials support effective osteoconduction, and when incorporated with bioactive molecules, they further enhanced this process [9]. However, these biomaterials are only very slowly remodeled and remain an integral part of the healed defect.

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Moreover, due to their fragile structure, they are typically used in combination with additional internal fixation when treating large bone defects [10]. Therefore, hydrogel matrices with in vivo degradation properties, matching tissue regeneration and the ability to promote tissue regenerative functions, have gained attention [11, 12]. Natural hydrogels, despite their excellent biocompatibility and inherent healing-promoting functions, have limited in vivo stability and cannot be easily adapted to specific needs of the healing environment [13].

Synthetic hydrogels, unlike natural hydrogels, offer the advantage of independently controlling and tailoring specific properties, such as provision of cell adhesion sites, proteolytic susceptibility, or growth factor binding sites through specific molecular design and synthesis processes [14–17]. Various synthetic hydrogel materials have been employed as matrices for bone tissue engineering and regeneration, with poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) being one of the most widely used due to its favorable properties [12, 18, 19]. We have previously described a transglutaminase cross-linked PEG hydrogel (TG-PEG) with a modular design that enables precise optimization to enhance specific cellular behaviors. This customization is achieved through the adjustment of various hydrogel parameters, including stiffness [20, 21]. Soft TG-PEG hydrogels containing matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-sensitive crosslinks and integrin-binding peptide Arg-Gly-Asp (RGD) have allowed cell infiltration and remodeling capabilities both in vitro and in vivo [3, 20, 21].

It is generally accepted that high substrate stiffness (11–30 kPa) is a key factor in osteogenic differentiation, as it regulates integrin-mediated adhesion and nanoscale ligand reorganization. Traction-dependent factors were shown to play a crucial role in the commitment of stem cells to an osteogenic lineage, ultimately supporting bone formation and regeneration [22]. However, increasing the stiffness of hydrogels from 75 to 3000 Pa significantly hindered the infiltration, spreading, and growth of encapsulated cells [3, 23]. This effect is largely attributed to the mesh size of hydrogels, where increasing stiffness through higher polymer concentrations and, consequently, higher cross-link density, requires more extensive proteolytic remodeling of the matrix. Therefore, in order to optimize cellular interactions, it is important to treat material stiffness and pore size as distinct design parameters and to minimize their interdependence as far as the system permits. Furthermore, the uniform properties of most bulk hydrogels throughout their volume do not allow the incorporation of diverse signaling molecules, potentially hindering optimal cell-material interactions [24, 25].

In recent years, microporous annealed microparticles (MAP), consisting of microgels of defined size and composition, have emerged as a promising solution for design of microporous scaffolds in tissue engineering [26, 27]. These materials allow for independent tuning of pore size, dictated by the void spaces between interconnected microgels, and stiffness, which is controlled by polymer concentration [28, 29]. Emerging evidence highlights the significance of the geometric properties of the cellular microenvironment as key regulators of cell behavior, influencing both nutrient diffusion and cellular responses [30]. Notably, convex surfaces have been shown to induce pronounced nuclear deformation through cytoskeletal forces, thereby activating mechanotransduction pathways that favor osteogenic

differentiation [31]. In addition to these geometric effects, the injectability of microgels enables minimally invasive delivery directly to the target site, offering a practical advantage in clinical applications. Together, these characteristics help to overcome several limitations associated with traditional bulk hydrogels for tissue regeneration [32–34]. Consistent with this, in vivo studies across multiple models have demonstrated the superior performance of microgel constructs compared to bulk hydrogels. Whereas bulk materials often exhibit slow remodeling and limited degradation, microgel constructs promote the formation of connective tissue in a substantial proportion of cases [30].

In this study, we investigated the relationship between microgel stiffness and cell behavior using a previously developed microfluidic chip to confine them [35]. We tested microgels made from varying levels of TG-PEG stiffness and different sizes to assess their effects on cell recruitment and spreading in vitro. Additionally, we explored YAP expression to understand how mechanical cues influence cellular responses. Extending our research to an ex vivo setting, we evaluated the recruitment of bone cells by seeding microgels into drilled holes in mouse calvaria bones. Through these approaches, we aimed to enhance our understanding of how engineered microenvironments can be utilized to modulate cellular behaviors, with significant implications for tissue engineering and regenerative medicine.

2 | Results

2.1 | Mechanical Characterization of TG-PEG Microgels

In order to precisely control their size, enzymatically crosslinked poly(ethylene glycol) (TG-PEG) microgels were synthesized using a microfluidic flow-focusing technique. For this, the n-PEG-MMP-Lys and n-PEG-Gln monomers were covalently cross-linked by the enzyme factor XIIIa in a 50 mM Tris buffer, with 50 mM calcium chloride serving as a cofactor to catalyze the reaction (Figure 1a). To prevent premature polymerization, the factor XIIIa solution was injected separately from the PEG precursor and cofactor solutions. Due to the differing densities of the two solutions, a distinct interface was formed (Figure 1b). The two components were then mixed at the downstream cross-junction, where the oil phase pinched the flow, enabling the formation of microgels. To promote cell adhesion and facilitate the visualization of microgels, 50 μM Lys-RGD and 50 μM Lys-FITC, which contained a FXIII substrate sequence, were incorporated into the PEG precursor solution. A scheme of the setup is shown in Figure S1.

The solutions were delivered at precise flow rates using calibrated syringe pumps. The volumetric flow rate of the PEG solution was maintained at a constant value of 2.1 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ to prevent backflow of the PEG into the factor XIIIa channel, which occurred at higher flow rates. To control the size of the microgels, the volumetric flow rate of the oil phase was varied. Three distinct microgel sizes were formed: small ($\varnothing = 56.2 \pm 4.1 \mu\text{m}$, oil flow rate = 1 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), medium ($\varnothing = 73.1 \pm 3.5 \mu\text{m}$, oil flow rate = 4 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), and large ($\varnothing = 97.5 \pm 5.7 \mu\text{m}$, oil flow rate = 13 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$). The relative frequency distribution of these sizes for 5 wt.% TG-PEG microgels is presented in Figure 1c.

FIGURE 1 | Formation and characterization of TG-PEG microgels and microgel assemblies. a) Schematic illustration of PEG hydrogel formation. The enzyme Factor XIIIa, together with calcium serving as a cofactor, catalyzes the cross-linking of n-PEG-MMP-Lys and n-PEG-Gln monomers. b) Microgel formation. The TG-PEG and FXIIIa phases converge at the Y-junction, initiating the crosslinking reaction. Droplet formation occurs downstream at the cross-junction as the aqueous phase is sheared by the oil phase, generating microgels. c) Relative frequency of microgel size distribution. d) Bulk storage modulus (G') of TG-PEG hydrogels formed with initial precursor concentrations of 1.7, 2, 5, and 7.5 wt.% ($n = 3$). e) Young's modulus of TG-PEG microgels with initial precursor concentrations of 2, 5, and 7.5 wt.% TG-PEG as determined by fluid AFM ($n = 20$). f) Pore recognition using the Regionprops3D algorithm. Representative slide from a Z-stack (left), post-processed image (center), and ball-fitted image (right). g) Interstitial spaces within the confinement chamber. Quantification of interstitial spaces between microgels with different stiffness, left ($n = 4$) and varying sizes, right ($n = 4$). Data in bar plots are represented as mean \pm SD. $**p < 0.01$, $****p < 0.0001$.

To investigate the effect of initial precursor concentrations on the stiffness, rheological properties of forming TG-PEG hydrogels from 1.7, 2, 5, and 7.5 wt.% precursor solutions were measured. Obtained stiffness values were 0.4, 1.3, 5.4, and 7 kPa, respectively (Figure 1d). In our study, 1.7 wt.% TG-PEG was employed to model the tissue compartment in the double-channel system, as described later. Next, TG-PEG microgels with initial polymer concentrations of 2, 5, and 7.5 wt.% were formed and the Young's moduli of individual microgels were tested with FluidFM to assess their mechanical behavior at the microscale (Figure 1e). A tipless probe with a fixed microgel via negative pressure was used to perform force-indentation measurements, applying controlled forces onto individual microgels to determine their elastic response. Microgels held at the aperture via negative pressure were approached onto the glass surface with a controlled force to perform force-indentation measurements (Figure S2). The obtained Young's moduli for 2, 5, and 7.5 wt.% TG-PEG microgels were 1.1, 3.7, and 4.5 kPa, respectively.

Next, to assess the influence of microgel properties on micropores, microgels were confined into the microfluidic chip and the average interstitial spaces between microgels were evaluated in fully packed channel areas. Full stacks were processed and analyzed using Python, following the pre-processing and post-processing steps outlined previously. For each stack, one optical plain was selected from the beginning, middle, and bottom, and the spaces were quantified for each selected slice using the snow partitioning algorithm. Ball fitting was then performed using the Regionprops3D function to estimate the pore diameter distribution. The results from these three focal plains were averaged to provide a representative measure of interstitial space size for each stack (Figure 1f). With 73 μm microgels the smallest interstitial areas were observed in the softest (1.1 kPa) TG-PEG microgels, with an average size of 30.9 μm . Slightly larger sizes were found in the confined 3.7 and 4.5 kPa TG-PEG microgels, with average diameters of 34.9 and 35.4 μm , respectively (Figure 1g). No significant differences in interstitial spaces were observed among the small, medium, and large 5 wt.% TG-PEG microgels, which had average sizes of 35.1, 35.4, and 35.4 μm , respectively (Figure 1g). The analysis of interstitial spaces in confined microgel environments highlights the influence of microgel stiffness on pore structure. While variations in microgel size at a constant concentration did not significantly affect space sizes between them—likely due to insufficient differences in dimension—microgel stiffness proved to be a key determinant. Softer (1.1 kPa) microgels resulted to have smaller spaces, a consequence of the higher deformability under confinement. This suggests that the mechanical properties of the microgel material play a crucial role in shaping pore formation and size.

2.2 | Influence of Microgel Properties on hBM-MSC Behavior

To explore if material stiffness guides cell spreading and mechanosensitive signaling, microgels with varying stiffness (1.1, 3.7, and 4.5 kPa, Figure 2a) and hBM-MSCs (1.6×10^7 cells mL^{-1}) were co-confined in single-channel microfluidic chips (Figure S3a). After culture with basal medium for 7 days, cells were fixed and stained for nuclei, F-actin, and YAP. Quantitative analysis on maximum projection confocal images revealed that hBM-MSCs

exhibited significantly greater spreading on stiffer compared to softer substrates. The 4.5 kPa TG-PEG hydrogel, which exhibited the highest stiffness, supported the largest cell spreading area, with a value of $499 \pm 94 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{nucleus}$, calculated by normalizing the cell area to the nuclei. This was followed by the 3.7 kPa and 1.1 kPa TG-PEG hydrogels, which displayed cell spreading areas of $485 \pm 73 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{nucleus}$ and $372 \pm 57 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{nucleus}$, respectively (Figure 2b). YAP activation was evident across all experimental conditions (Figure 2a). For clarity, Figure S4 displays confocal images with the F-actin and YAP channels presented individually. Comparable to cell spreading, the nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio of YAP correlated with stiffness, with 13 ± 3 , 27.6 ± 9 , and $27.8\% \pm 6\%$ for 1.1, 3.7, and 4.5 kPa microgels, respectively (Figure 2c). Overall, the data indicated an increased nuclear localization of YAP in response to stiffer materials, suggesting a translocation of the protein toward the nucleus, which is typically associated with enhanced transcriptional activity and cellular responses to mechanical cues.

Next, TG-PEG microgels of intermediate stiffness (3.7 kPa) were selected to further investigate the impact of microgel size on cell behavior (Figure 2d). The analysis revealed an enhanced hBM-MSC spreading on the largest microgels. Specifically, the average spreading areas were $557 \pm 75 \mu\text{m}^2$ for smaller microgels and $658 \pm 66 \mu\text{m}^2$ for larger microgels (Figure 2e). In line with the established relationship between YAP activity and substrate stiffness, no significant differences in YAP expression were observed across the different microgel size conditions (Figure 2f). This demonstrates that material stiffness regulates cell behavior by enhancing cell spreading and YAP activation, with stiffer substrates promoting YAP nuclear localization. Microgel size has minimal impact on YAP expression, underscoring stiffness as the primary factor influencing cellular responses.

2.3 | Microgel Assemblies with Increased Stiffness Promote hBM-MSC Recruitment

To investigate the influence of microgel stiffness on hBM-MSC recruitment and migration, a double-channel microfluidic chips that mimicked the cell recruitment phase of tissue healing was employed. For this, the “tissue mimicking” chambers were filled with soft (0.4 kPa) bulk TG-PEG and $0.25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ collagen I hydrogel containing encapsulated hBM-MSCs (1.6×10^7 cells mL^{-1}). Then 1.1, 3.7 and 4.5 kPa TG-PEG microgels were confined in the immediately adjacent “recruitment” chamber and cultured for 4 days in basal medium with 100 ng mL^{-1} PDGF-BB. Cell recruitment was observed in fixed and nuclei and F-actin-stained samples (Figure 3a). For each chip, multiple randomized regions of interest were selected in which the migrated distances of a total of 706, 1106, and 1393 cell nuclei were quantified in 1.1, 3.7, and 4.5 kPa microgels compartments, respectively. The average distance hBM-MSCs traveled was 289 μm when cultured in the 4.5 kPa microgels, followed by 199 μm in the 3.7 kPa microgels, and 149 μm in the 1.1 kPa microgels. Although there was no significant difference between the 1.1 and the 3.7 kPa conditions, both exhibited significantly reduced cell movement compared to the 4.5 kPa microgels, which supported greatest cell migration (Figure 3b). Additionally, in this in vitro assay, spreading evaluations showed a significant increased spreading on stiffer materials compared to softer ones. Average cell

FIGURE 2 | Influence of microgel properties on hBM-MSC behavior. YAP expression in hBM-MSCs cultured with microgels of varying a–c) stiffness and d–f) sizes. The top row (10x magnification) displays packed microgels (grey). The middle row shows maximum intensity projection of confocal stacks (z-step 2.41 μm , total height 70 μm) of cells stained for nuclei (blue), F-actin (red), and YAP (green). The bottom row presents a higher magnification (40x) of the cellular regions. Actin spreading area in response to microgels, b) stiffness ($n > 6$), and e) size ($n = 5$). Quantification of cell spreading, as indicated by F-actin area, for microgels with different properties. d) Nuclear-to-cytoplasmic YAP intensity ratio. Measurement of YAP localization in cells seeded with microgels of varying c) stiffness ($n = 6$) and f) sizes ($n = 5$), indicating mechanotransduction responses. For each “n”, more than 82 cells were analyzed. Data in bar plots are presented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

FIGURE 3 | Influence of microgel stiffness on hBM-MSC recruitment. a) Representative images showing cell invasion into the microgel compartment after 4 days in culture for stiffness values of 1.1 kPa (left), 3.7 kPa (center), and 4.5 kPa (right). Nuclei = blue, F-Actin = red. Migration from the interface, indicated by the dotted line, is shown in the upper row (maximum intensity projection of confocal stacks, z-step 2.41 μm , total height 70 μm), and zoomed-in images are presented in the lower row (maximum intensity projection of confocal stacks, z-step 2.41 μm , total height 82 μm). b) Quantification of the migration distance of hBM-MSCs from the interface. ($n \geq 11$). c) Measurement of F-actin area spread around the microgels ($n \geq 11$). Number of cell nuclei quantified in microgel compartments: 706 (1.1 kPa), 1106 (3.7 kPa), and 1393 (4.5 kPa). Data in plots are represented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$. Different donors are shown in different colors.

spreading area was $446 \pm 78 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{nucleus}$ on the softest (1.1 kPa) microgels, while for the 3.7 and 4.5 kPa microgels, it increased to 491 ± 93 and $603 \pm 135 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{nucleus}$, respectively (Figure 3c). These findings highlight the crucial role of material stiffness in influencing hBM-MSC behavior, particularly in terms of migration and spreading, which is essential for tissue regeneration.

2.4 | Increased Microgel Stiffness Promotes Osteogenic Gene Expression

To further validate the osteogenic differentiation of cultured hBM-MSCs on microgels, RT-qPCR was used to assess the mRNA expression levels of key osteogenic markers, including the osteogenic transcription factors SP7 (osterix) and RUNX2,

which play critical roles in regulating osteoblast development, alkaline phosphatase (ALP), an early marker of osteogenic cell differentiation, collagen type 1 (COL1) and integrin binding sialoprotein (IBSP), proteins of the bone matrix. For this, hBM-MSCs were cultured for 14 days on microgels of varying stiffness in the presence of osteogenic medium (OM) or encapsulated in bulk hydrogels with and without OM. Gene expression levels were quantified relative to a reference gene (e.g., GAPDH) and the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method was applied to evaluate quantitative differences between groups. Figure 4 presents data from one representative hBM-MSC donor; corresponding results from additional two donors are included in Figure S5. The expression of both transcription factors, OSX (Figure 4a) and RUNX2 (Figure 4b), as well as the early osteogenic differentiation marker ALP (Figure 4c) and IBSP (Figure 4e), significantly increased with elevated microgel stiffness. However, when compared to hydrogel-encapsulated hBM-MSCs, only the expressions of ALP and IBSP were significantly improved. COL1 expression was higher in cells adhering to the microgels than in cells cultured within the bulk (Figure 4d). These results show that increased microgel stiffness promotes early osteogenic differentiation in hBM-MSCs, with elevated ALP, RUNX2, OSX, and IBSP expression. However, full osteoblast maturation may require longer culture periods.

2.5 | Stiff Microgels are Infiltrated by Bone Defect-Derived Cells

Finally, to mimic treatment of bone defects *ex vivo*, small holes were drilled in calvaria bones freshly harvested from Foxn1tm mice with 19G needles and filled with FITC-labelled microgels or bulk hydrogel controls (Figure S6). After 7 days of culture in the presence of 100 ng mL⁻¹ PDGF-BB, confocal imaging of actin and DAPI-stained treatment sites displayed a notable cell ingrowth and tight wrapping around microgels (Figure 5a). In contrast, cells were unable to infiltrate the bulk hydrogel controls. To further assess the impact of microgel stiffness on cellular recruitment, the number of cells surrounding the microgels was quantified and normalized by the number of microgels present in each hole (Figure 5b). Interestingly, microgel stiffness significantly influenced the number of recruited cells. Specifically, microgels with 1.1, 3.7, and 4.5 kPa were surrounded by an average of 1.2, 2.8, and 3.2 cells per microgel, respectively, showing a clear correlation between microgel stiffness and cell recruitment. These results highlight the importance of stiffness in bone regeneration, with microgel-based scaffolds promoting cell migration and tissue integration. Higher stiffness enhances cell recruitment, suggesting that optimizing material properties can improve early-stage therapy outcomes for bone defects.

3 | Discussion

In this study, we developed synthetic microgel aggregates with optimized properties for the recruitment, growth, and differentiation of bone progenitor cells. By tuning the interstitial spaces and the stiffness, we were able to demonstrate superior *in vitro* and *ex vivo* recruitment capabilities of microgel agglomerates with increased stiffness compared to bulk hydrogels.

Bone regeneration on provisional blood clots or biomaterials support the coordinated cellular activities at the defect site [36, 37]. It is also well established that rigid substrates are more effective for promoting the osteogenic differentiation of bone progenitor cells. However, synthetic hydrogels, due their mesh size at the nano scale, promote bone regeneration only when their formulations are soft enough to allow for efficient host cell infiltration [3]. To engineer stiff hydrogels with adequate pore sizes conducive to cellular infiltration, we developed enzymatically cross-linked TG-PEG microgels, utilizing a microfluidic flow-focusing technique. By systematically manipulating the flow rates and concentrations of the PEG precursor and cross-linking enzyme solutions, introduced from distinct microfluidic channels, we successfully obtained microgels exhibiting low, medium, and high degrees of stiffness. Additionally, by adjusting the flow rate of the oil phase, we achieved microgels characterized by highly uniform small ($56.2 \pm 4.1 \mu\text{m}$), medium ($73.1 \pm 3.5 \mu\text{m}$), and large ($97.5 \pm 5.7 \mu\text{m}$) sizes, reproducing the earlier shown reliability and tunability of the microfluidic approach in generating microgels [34, 38].

Pore size and distribution, additionally to affecting nutrient and signaling molecule diffusion, have previously been shown to play a key role in providing space for cell growth and migration within a biomaterial [39, 40]. Our evaluations revealed a pore distribution with sizes in the range of cell diameters in all microgel assemblies. As expected, the softest (1.1 kPa) microgels formed the smallest interstitial pores, whereas stiffer (3.7 and 4.5 kPa) microgels exhibited slightly larger pore spaces. Interestingly, in agglomerates of microgels with increasing size, interstitial pore size remained relatively constant, suggesting that in this setup of physically confined microgels, matrix stiffness plays the more dominant role in defining pore architecture.

In this study, hBM-MSC exhibited increased spreading on stiffer microgels. This observation is consistent with previous studies that identified size and stiffness as key parameters to influence the cell-material interactions [39, 40]. Indeed, rigid matrices facilitated cytoskeletal extension and migration by providing strong adhesion sites and traction forces [35, 41, 42]. YAP was shown to transmit mechanical cues by translocating from the cytoplasm to the nucleus, where it regulates expression of genes related to cell proliferation, survival, and migration [43–45]. Our results demonstrated a clear relationship between YAP localization and material stiffness, with YAP being more nuclear on stiffer microgels ($27.6\% \pm 9\%$ and $27.8\% \pm 6\%$ on 3.7 and 4.5 kPa microgels, respectively) and mostly cytoplasmic on soft (1.1 kPa) microgels. Since substrate microstructures were shown to have a significant impact on cell adhesion and spreading [46, 47], we investigated the impact of microgel size on cell spreading and YAP activation. To isolate the effect of microgel size, we maintained a constant microgel stiffness of 3.7 kPa throughout the study. Although cell spreading increased slightly on larger microgels, YAP localization remained unchanged. Overall, the study highlighted the central role of material stiffness in regulating cell behavior, particularly cell spreading and mechanosensitive signaling. The observed increase in cell spreading and nuclear YAP localization on stiffer substrates demonstrated that mechanical cues strongly influence cellular responses. These findings support the view that stiffness acts as a key driver of mechanotransduction by promoting

FIGURE 4 | Quantification of osteogenic gene expression. Gene expression analysis of the osteogenic markers: (a) OSX, (b) RUNX2, (c) ALP, (d) COL1, and (e) IBSP. GAPDH was used as the reference gene for normalization, with data compared to the bulk hydrogel without OM ($n \geq 3$). Data in bar plots are represented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

YAP nuclear translocation, which is associated with increased transcriptional activity. Previous studies further showed that exposure of hMSCs to sufficiently stiff hydrogels can lead to irreversible YAP activation and bias stem cells toward osteogenic differentiation. Taken together, these results indicate that matrix stiffness is a decisive regulator of stem cell fate through its control of mechanosensitive pathways [48].

Additionally, while stiffness was the primary factor influencing cell spreading and YAP activation, microgel size within the tested stiffness range did not significantly affect YAP expression. This suggested that, for the given stiffness range, cell behavior is predominantly governed by material stiffness rather than microgel size variations. This aligns with a growing body of evidence indicating that mechanosensitive signaling pathways,

FIGURE 5 | Microgel-mediated recruitment of cells from bone defects. a) Representative images showing cellular invasion from the edges of the hole into TG-PEG microgel assemblies with low (first row), intermediate (second row), and high stiffness (third row), as well as soft bulk TG-PEG hydrogels (fourth row). Nuclei are stained blue, F-actin is red, and microgels/bulk appear green. b) Quantitative analysis of the number of migrated cells per microgel ($n \geq 4$). Data in bar plots are represented as mean \pm SD. $*p < 0.05$.

such as those involving YAP, are predominantly influenced by the stiffness of the extracellular matrix, rather than by the size or shape of the microenvironment [49, 50].

However, it is important to note that, although we aimed to decouple material stiffness from pore size, softer microgels

produced smaller interstitial spaces. This observation suggests that a complete decoupling of these parameters is our setup is not yet achievable. This could be due to increased deformation or compression of softer microgels within the microfluidic chip during assembly, which can reduce the effective interparticle spacing.

Our *in vitro* osteogenic differentiation assays reveal a more pronounced osteogenic differentiation of hBM-SCs when cultured on the surface of microgels, compared to those cultured in soft hydrogels. This correlates with previous findings of hBM-MSCs cultured and differentiated on substrates with different levels of stiffness [51, 52]. In the context of 3D cultures, these findings suggest that increased substrate stiffness could be beneficial for promoting osteogenic differentiation, provided the biomaterial used supports unrestricted cell spreading and growth [53, 54]. Hydrogels with interconnected micropores, which facilitate nutrient and oxygen diffusion while maintaining stiffness, are ideal candidates for these conditions.

Bone regeneration critically depends on the accumulation and differentiation of bone progenitor cells from the adjacent defective tissue. Using our earlier developed double-channel microfluidic system [35], we showed that hBM-MSCs from bone mimetic tissues (represented by hBM-MSCs seeded hydrogels) invade adjacent microgel assemblies when stimulated with the migration-inducing factor PDGF-BB. Importantly, in this study, stiffer microgels facilitated greater cell migration, aligning with the established principle that stiff substrates promote motility by providing stronger adhesion and traction forces for movement [55].

Our *in vitro* findings corroborated with observations in our more complex *ex vivo* model, where mouse calvaria bone defects were treated with different microgel stiffness and defined migration-inducing conditions. Importantly, in this model, host cells were largely absent inside of soft (0.4 kPa) bulk hydrogels, whereas in all tested (medium sized) microgels host cells infiltration was observed. Remarkably, the microgels with the highest stiffness (4.5 kPa) showed best cell infiltration when compared to the softest (1.1 kPa) microgels. The limited cell infiltration into the bulk hydrogel highlights the challenge for cells to overcome the nanoscale porosity, while macro-sized pores supported the attachment and growth of cells. This suggests that the enhanced cell recruitment observed in our study can be attributed to the macro-sized interstitial spaces between the individual microgels, which create a more favorable environment for host cell infiltration. Furthermore, the microgels themselves acted as a physical scaffold, supporting cellular attachment and growth, which may have further contributed to the observed cellular recruitment. Future studies are needed to better understand the nature of the recruited cells, their interactions with the microgel scaffold, and their spatial distribution within the defect site.

An ever-expanding range of hydrogel modifications is becoming available, offering the possibility of combining and integrating them into microgels with different backbone and cross-linking designs [56, 57]. In addition to the size and stiffness variations presented here, these modifications can be engineered to exhibit a wide variety of properties enabling differential cell adhesion, controlled degradation, bioactive factor binding, and release [58, 59]. Therefore, microgel assemblies will likely become an incredibly versatile and customizable platform for designing homogeneously or even heterogeneously biomaterials tailored for specific *in vitro* and *in vivo* applications. They could serve as an ideal scaffold material, supporting active cell infiltration and promoting new bone formation [60].

4 | Conclusion

In this work, we emphasize the critical role of mechanical properties and pore structure in determining the behavior of microgels for bone regeneration. Our findings demonstrate that microgel stiffness, rather than size, significantly influences the behavior of hBM-MSCs, promoting greater cell spreading, migration, and recruitment in stiffer environments. Moreover, our *in vitro* and *ex vivo* studies highlight the importance of interstitial pores between microgels in facilitating cellular infiltration into defect sites. These results suggest that microgels, due to their tunable stiffness and porous architecture, offer distinct advantages over conventional bulk hydrogels. Therefore, engineered microgel assemblies, by more closely mimicking the properties of the natural ECM, provide an environment that supports tissue regeneration, particularly in the context of bone healing.

Our findings underscore the potential of microgel-based scaffolds as versatile platforms for enhancing tissue repair. The ability to fine-tune the stiffness of the microgels offers a promising strategy for addressing challenging bone defects, where efficient cell infiltration is essential for successful healing. While our study presents a strong case for the use of TG-PEG microgels, further research is needed to optimize their properties and explore their long-term effects on tissue integration, bone formation, and remodeling.

5 | Experimental Section/Methods

5.1 | Synthesis of 8-Arm TG-PEG

TG-PEG was synthesized as previously described [20, 21]. In brief, 8-arm PEG-VS (40 kDa, PEG-vinylsulfone) was functionalized with either a glutamine acceptor peptide (Gln; H-NQEV SPL-ERCG-NH₂, Bachem) or a matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-degradable lysine donor peptide (MMP-sensitive Lys; Ac-FKGG-GPQGIWGQ-ERCG-NH₂, Bachem), both of which serve as substrates for factor XIII (FXIIIa). The peptides were conjugated to the PEG-VS through a Michael-type addition reaction in triethanolamine (Sigma-Aldrich) for 2 h at 37°C and pH 8.0. The resulting n-PEG-Gln and n-PEG-MMP-Lys were then crosslinked by factor XIIIa to form hydrogel networks. During this crosslinking process, the adhesion ligand H-FKGGRGDSPG-NH₂ (Lys-RGD; Bachem) and fluorescein isothiocyanate-labelled peptides Ac-FKGGK(fluorescein)-NH₂ (Lys-FITC; Bachem) was incorporated. The reaction was carried out in Tris buffer (50 mM, pH 7.6) with calcium chloride (50 mM). After the addition of factor XIIIa, the solution was quickly vortexed, and polymerization occurred within approximately 3 min.

5.2 | Microfluidic Chip Production

Microfluidic chips were produced as described previously [35]. Briefly, the microfluidic chips were designed using Fusion360 (Autodesk) and fabricated through a photolithography process. To create the master molds, SU-8 photoresist (GM1070, Gersteltec Engineering Solutions, Switzerland) was poured onto

plasma-cleaned silicon wafers (Si-Wafer, Siegart Wafer) and spin-coated for 30 s at 550 rpm, followed by 2 s at 2000 rpm, achieving a thickness of 170 μm . The wafer was then prebaked at 65°C for 3 min and at 95°C for 9 min. The coated wafer was exposed to UV light through a photomask (MicroLitho), followed by a postbake at 65°C for 2 min and at 95°C for 4 min. The unexposed photoresist was then removed with a developer (PGMEA, Merck) solution. Finally, the wafer was hardbaked at 200°C for 10 min.

The microfluidic chips were then fabricated using standard soft-lithography techniques. A mixture of PDMS monomer and curing agent (RT 601 A/B, Elastosil) was combined in a 9:1 ratio, poured over the master mold, degassed for 10 min and finally cured at 70°C for 30 min. Once polymerized, the PDMS was carefully peeled off the mold, and inlet and outlet holes were punched using a 20G precision hole punch (Syneo). The PDMS was then bonded to a glass slide (Menzel-Glaser, Germany) for droplet generation devices or to a cover slip (25 mm diameter, 1.5 thickness; EpreDia) for culture devices, after both surfaces were treated with air plasma for 1 min. The assembled devices were placed on a hot plate at 120°C for 2 h to ensure proper adhesion.

5.3 | Cell Culture

Human bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stromal cells (hBM-MSCs) were extracted from bone marrow aspirates taken from donors undergoing hip surgeries at Universitätsspital Basel, with no additional health complications reported (Prof. Kummer; approval date 26/03/2007 Ref. Number 78/07), after informed consent [61], and cultured in Minimum Essential Medium alpha (MEM α , Gibco) culture medium.

MEM α was supplied with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS, Gibco) and 1% in volume of Penicillin-Streptomycin (P/S). Basic fibroblast growth factor (FGF-2; Peprotech) was added at a final concentration of 5 ng mL⁻¹.

Cells were detached with 0.05% Trypsin-EDTA (Gibco) when the flask reached a 80–90% confluence. Cells were used between passages 3 and 7. All cultures were grown in incubator at 37°C with 5% CO₂.

5.4 | Microgel Production

Microgels were synthesized using a microfluidic technique that involved water-in-oil emulsification with a flow-focusing device [56]. The chip design featured an upstream Y-junction to separately channel the PEG precursor and crosslinking agent feeds, allowing precise control over the initiation of the polymerization reaction, along with a downstream cross-junction. The initiation of the crosslinking reaction occurred at the Y-junction, while droplet formation happened at the downstream of the cross-junction by focusing the aqueous phase with an oil phase (Droplet Generation Oil for probes, Biorad Laboratories Inc.). A Cetoni neMESYS syringe pump, paired with a Cetoni base 120 power adapter, regulated the flow of both the aqueous and oil phases. The PEG precursors, mixed with fluorescein isothiocyanate-

labelled peptides (Lys-FITC; Bachem) for further visualization of microgels, was delivered at a steady rate of 2 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$, while the oil flow rate was adjusted between 1 and 13 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ to control the microgel size. The droplets were collected in a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube containing oil and allowed to polymerize at room temperature (RT) for 30 min. After crosslinking, the microgels were separated from the oil by centrifugation at 14 000 $\times g$ for 5 min. The microgels were first washed twice with basal culture medium, followed by two washes with 0.025% Tween20 (Sigma-Aldrich) in 1x PBS (BioConcept). Afterward, the microgels were washed four additional times with basal culture medium. After each washing step, the supernatant was carefully removed, the respective washing solution was added and the microgels were then vortexed and centrifuged at 14 000 $\times g$ for 5 min. The oil-free microgels were stored in basal culture medium at 4°C for later use.

5.5 | Seeding of Microfluidic Chips

Both single- and double-channel microfluidic chips were first secured in a 6-well plate by adding PBS (1 μL) between the plate and the chip glass to immobilize them.

For the single-channel chips, a master mix was prepared by combining 60 μL of 0.5% methylcellulose (MC) in PBS, 10 μL of packed microgels, and 10 μL of hBM-MSCs at a concentration of 1.6×10^7 cells mL⁻¹ in basal medium. Twenty microliters of the master mix were then pipetted into the culture channel of the chip, filling it with the microgels. To prevent the backflow of microgels, a 2 mm tungsten wire (ADVENT Research Material Ltd.) was inserted into the inlet hole. After seeding, 200 μL of basal medium was added to the two lateral channels, and the medium was changed after 4 days. The samples were kept in culture for 7 days in total.

For the double-channel chips, two separate master mixes were prepared. In the tissue-mimicking chamber, PEG precursor solutions were made as described earlier, at a final concentration of 1.7 wt%. To enhance tissue-mimicking properties, 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of bovine collagen I (Advanced Biomatrix) was added. hBM-MSCs were encapsulated at a final concentration of 2×10^7 cells mL⁻¹, and the cross-linking enzyme FXIIIa (10 U mL⁻¹) was introduced. After brief vortexing, 2 μL of the mix were injected into the tissue chamber. To prevent cells from settling at the bottom during polymerization, the plate was rotated up and down several times. The bulk gel was left to polymerize for 10 min before flushing the other channels with 100 μL of basal medium. Subsequently, microgel suspensions were prepared by mixing 0.5% MC in PBS (60 μL) with packed microgels (20 μL), which were then injected into the microfluidic channels as previously described. After seeding, basal medium (200 μL), supplemented with PDGF-BB (100 ng mL⁻¹, Peprotech), was added to the lateral channels. The samples were cultured for 4 days.

For both experimental setups, 2 mL of PBS was added to the interwell spaces of the six-well plate, creating a humidified chamber to minimize medium evaporation during culture. All samples were maintained in an incubator at 37°C with 5% CO₂ and humidified air.

5.6 | Osteogenic Gene Expression Quantification

For gene expression analysis, hBM-MSCs were cultured for 14 days in osteogenic medium (OM). The OM formulation consisted of MEM α (Gibco) supplemented with 1% P/S, 10% FBS (Gibco), 0.05 mg mL⁻¹ ascorbic acid, 10 mM β -glycerophosphate, 10 mM HEPES (Sigma-Aldrich), 1 mM sodium pyruvate, 2 mM L-glutamine, and BMP-2 (100 μ g mL⁻¹).

For seeding, 10 μ L of a 4 \times 10⁶ cells mL⁻¹ hBM-MSC suspension was mixed with microgels (10 μ L) and deposited into a 1 mm diameter well, created by using a biopsy punch in a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) block. At the end of the culture period, RNA was extracted by carefully collecting the cell-microgel mixture with a spatula. Cells were enzymatically released by treating each well with collagenase A solution (200 μ L, 2 mg mL⁻¹ in PBS) and incubating at 37°C for 15 min. Following vortexing, samples underwent an additional 15-min incubation at 37°C. The digested cell suspensions were centrifuged at 300 \times g for 10 min, and total RNA was extracted from the resulting pellets using the RNeasy Micro Kit (Qiagen), following the manufacturer's protocol.

For reverse transcription quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR), 120 ng of total RNA was converted into complementary DNA (cDNA) using the High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems) in a 20 μ L reaction volume. RT-qPCR was performed using a ViiA 7 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems) with TaqMan Universal PCR Master Mix (Applied Biosystems) and specific TaqMan gene expression assays. The analyzed osteogenic markers included RUNX2 (Hs01047973_m1), SP7 (Hs01866874_s1), ALPL (Hs01029144_m1), IBSP (Hs00913377_m1), COL1 (Hs00164004_m1), and GAPDH (Hs02758991_g1) serving as the endogenous reference gene for normalization. Relative gene expression levels were calculated using the 2^{- $\Delta\Delta$ CT} method and reported as fold change relative to control samples.

5.7 | Seeding of Bones

Calvaria bones were extracted from euthanized HsdCpb:NMRI-Foxn1nu and B6/J-Z-2021-Crl female and male mice (Envigo/Inotiv). The veterinary offices of the Swiss cantons of Zürich approved all animal procedures under ethical licenses (Application No. ZH167/2023). A small incision was made through the skin at the base of the skull, and the bone was carefully separated. Under sterile conditions in a biosafety cabinet, excess soft tissue was gently removed using autoclaved tweezers. The calvaria was then divided into four pieces, and each piece was punctured using a 19G needle. The bone fragments were then secured to a 24-well plate using 2% TG-PEG hydrogel, which had been prepared as described earlier. Packed microgels or 1.7 wt.% TG-PEG bulk hydrogels were placed into the holes in the bone fragments. To support cell culture, 1 mL of basal medium supplemented with PDGF-BB (100 ng mL⁻¹, Peprotech) was added to each well, with medium changes occurring every 4 days. All samples were incubated at 37°C with 5% CO₂ and humidified air.

5.8 | Rheological Characterization of TG-PEG

Rheological characterization of bulk TG-PEG gels was conducted using a strain-controlled shear rheometer (MCR 302e, Anton Paar). Data were collected with an 8 mm parallel-plate (PP08, Anton Paar) geometry. To prevent evaporation during measurement, silicon oil was applied around the samples. Immediately after the addition of factor XIIIa, drops of the gel solution (20 μ L) were pipetted onto the plate and the acquisition of the data was initiated. Gelation time, along with the storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli, were measured through oscillatory strain tests conducted over time at a strain amplitude of 4% ($\gamma = 4\%$) and an angular frequency of 1 rad s⁻¹ ($\omega = 1$ rad s⁻¹), conditions that fall within the linear viscoelastic (LVE) region, as outlined in the literature [62].

The Young's modulus of microgels was measured using a Fluidic force microscopy (FluidFM) system (FlexAFM-near-infrared scan head with a C3000 controller driven by the EasyScan2 software, Nanosurf AG, Switzerland) equipped with commercial tipless silicon nitride probes (Cytosurge AG, Switzerland) featuring an 8- μ m circular aperture [63]. Their spring constant was determined using the thermal tuning method [64–67], obtaining a value of 2.13 N m⁻¹. Deflection sensitivity was determined before each experiment by averaging the slopes from four forward force-distance curves acquired on the glass in 2 mL PBS (Thermo Fisher, USA). Microgels were sedimented onto the glass-bottom petri dish (WillcoWells, Netherlands) in 2 mL PBS. Individual microgels were immobilized by applying a negative pressure of -300 mbar at the aperture of the probe which was pre-filled with 10 μ L of a 1 mg mL⁻¹ Sulforhodamine B (acid form) solution (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) prepared in Milli-Q water [68, 69]. Indentation was performed at a constant approach speed of 2 μ m s⁻¹ toward the petri dish until reaching a setpoint in the range of 250–600 nN in contact mode. For each microgel formulation, force-distance curves were acquired from 20 individual microgels. The contact point was defined as the final peak observed in the variance ratio analysis, following established methods [70]. Then the resulting curves were fitted using the Hertzian contact model [71], assuming a spherical indenter with a contact radius corresponding to the microgel size and a Poisson's ratio (ν) of 0.5, to extract the Young's modulus (E).

5.9 | Fixation and Staining

Samples were first rinsed twice with PBS (100 μ L, Gibco) before 4% Paraformaldehyde (PFA, Artechemis) was added for microfluidic chips, and 500 μ L for bone samples. The samples were then incubated at room temperature (RT) for 30 min, followed by two washes with PBS. For permeabilization and blocking, a buffer was prepared containing 1% Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA, AppliChem) in PBS and 0.3% Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich). The samples were incubated with this solution at RT for 60 min.

For primary antibody incubation, the staining solution consisted of 1% BSA in PBS, 0.1% Triton X-100, and the primary antibody (YAP, sc101199, Santa Cruz) diluted to 1:200. For each well, 100 μ L (microfluidic chips) or 500 μ L (bone samples) of this staining solution was added, and the plate was incubated overnight at 4°C.

Following primary incubation, the samples were washed twice with PBS.

For secondary antibody incubation, the staining solution contained 1% BSA in PBS, 0.1% Triton X-100, 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, DAPI; Sigma-Aldrich), 1:4,000 Phalloidin-Rhodamine (Invitrogen, R415), and a secondary antibody at a 1:200 dilution. A volume of 100 μL was added for microfluidic chips and 500 μL for bone samples. The plate was wrapped in aluminum foil and incubated overnight at 4°C. After secondary incubation, the samples were washed three times with PBS.

5.10 | Image Acquisition and Processing

During the culture, the samples' morphology was imaged using a LEICA Inverted DMI6000B fluorescence microscope. Z-stacks of fixed and stained samples were acquired with the inverse confocal laser scanning microscope Leica STELLARIS 5 (CLSM). Fiji was employed for image analysis and processing [72].

5.11 | Microgels Size Distribution, Porosity, and Pore Diameter Analysis of Confined Microgel Constructs

The size distribution of FITC-labeled microgels was analyzed using confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM). Z-stack images of the confined microgels were captured (pixel size of 1.14 \times 1.14 μm , 25 slices with step size of 2.41 μm). The measurements were performed through the Fiji software. A median filter with a radius of 2 was applied to each image, which was then manually thresholded and binarized. The "Analyze Particles" tool was used to measure the diameters of the microgels. For porosity and pore diameter analyses, full z-stacks as described were utilized. Image processing and analysis were carried out in Python (script available on GitHub). In brief, individual stacks underwent pre-processing, which involved contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE), Gaussian blurring, and local Otsu thresholding. Post-processing steps included applying a median filter three times and performing morphological opening and closing. Pore sizes were measured using the snow partitioning algorithm and 3D region properties (Regionprops3D) for ball fitting [73].

5.12 | Yes-Associated Protein (YAP) Analysis

Fiji software (National Institutes of Health, USA) was employed for image analyses. Initially, the multichannel fluorescence images were split into their constituent channels. For this study, we focused on the DAPI channel for nuclear identification and the YAP channel for our protein of interest.

The threshold was adjusted until all nuclei were clearly distinguishable from the background and then applied, followed by a watershed algorithm to separate adjoining nuclei. All nuclei were selected by creating a selection and the region of interest (ROI) was saved for subsequent analyses.

For YAP intensity measurements, the channel image was duplicated. Thresholds were adjusted on both the original and duplicate images to optimize the signal-to-noise ratio. The previously saved nuclear ROI was applied to both images. For nuclear intensity quantification, the areas outside the nuclear ROI were cleared. Measurements were performed including parameters as area, integrated density and mean gray value. Cytoplasmic intensity was quantified by creating a selection of the cytoplasmic areas and measuring the same parameters as for the nuclear intensity.

5.13 | Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis of data was carried out using GraphPad Prism software. One-way ANOVA test and *t*-test were performed, as respectively stated in figure captions. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. The symbols *, **, ***, and **** were used to denote $p < 0.05$, 0.01, 0.001, and 0.0001, respectively. All data reported are mean \pm standard deviation.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) grant nos. 205321_204318 and 310030E_202429. Confocal imaging was performed with equipment maintained by the Center for Microscopy and Image Analysis, University of Zurich. H. G. was supported by the European Union's HORIZON.1.2 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101120146 (DN "NanoRAM" to T. Z.).

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Funding

This work was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) grant nos. 205321_204318 and 310030E_202429.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting file: adfm73561-sup-0001-SuppMat.docx